

Step-by-Step Instructions (JASP GUI)

1. **Open JASP** and load the appropriate CSV template:
 - Template_outcomes_inst_qualityBNA.csv
 - **or** Template_outcomes_inst_quality_attitudes_BNA.csv
2. Go to the **top menu bar** and select:
Modules → Network
(This activates the network analysis options)
3. Then, on the top ribbon, go to:
Network → **Bayesian**
(Not Classical! Select the “Bayesian Network Analysis” option specifically.)
4. In the **left panel**, a new analysis will appear titled:
Bayesian Network Analysis or similar.
5. At the analysis panel, proceed with:
 - **Select variables:** tick BTI variables (and attitudes, if applicable).
 - Under **Structure Learning**, choose:
 - Estimator: EBICglasso
 - γ (gamma) value: recommended 0.25
 - Enable: *Edge inclusion probabilities, Expected influence, and Centrality plots, etc.*